

A COGNITIVE APPROACH TO LANGUAGE UNITS

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ABSTRACT: The study explores a cognitive approach to language units, emphasizing that language serves as an integral system for societal communication and expression of thoughts. It posits that language is not an isolated system but deeply interconnected with cognitive processes, reflecting our perceptual, conceptual, and social faculties. Key language units such as phonemes, morphemes, words, and sentences are analyzed not just structurally but in terms of their cognitive representations and processes.

KEYWORDS: cognitive linguistics, language units, phonemes, morphemes, mental lexicon, syntax, language and thought, cognitive neuroscience, perception, categorization, communication.

The language is whole, regardless of groups and classes which serves society to get in touch with each other. Language is an important means of expression. Speak thoughtfully relationship is a complex process. Language exists as an expression of thought, its own in turn, thought is a complex process that occurs based on language. Language is formed in both thought and work processes in personal society. Language units - phoneme, morpheme, word, sentence as a whole, integrated with logical concepts (emotion, perception, thinking).

As a means of system, language is:

1. Communication is a relational function. This function of language is to serve as a means of communication in society. This is the main social function of language. Language signs communicate it - to distinguish language from other means of communication, a social phenomenon can be interpreted as language communication is a relationship with society as an important tool, its culture, life is regularly connected with every process in the style and labor activity. People express their thoughts, feelings and spiritual experiences and - they affect each other.

2. The role of emotional impact of language. How language expresses certain information and affects the listener is emotional – affective is a task. Expressing messages, intuition and excitement, desire forms the basis of the task of emotional impact. Different figurative language in this tool, including modal words, which do not require answering questions, order changes, etc.

3. Collecting function of language. Language communication is not only a means of communication, but also emotional. It is not only an expression of influence, but it must function as a collection. Language is a means of inter-ethnic communication, as a means of transferring accumulated knowledge and experiences from generation to generation is considered. This function of language is the main one in the cognitive process. Direct contact - during the relationship the functions of naming and expressing thoughts of the language are revealed. Independent words, compound nouns, phrases, and term nominative units are considered, and the different forms of the sentence are the unity of thought¹.

The study of language has long been a central focus in the field of linguistics, and over the years, various theoretical approaches have emerged to understand the complex nature of human communication. One such approach, known as Cognitive Linguistics, has gained significant traction in recent decades, offering a unique perspective on the relationship between language and cognition (Croft & Cruse, 2004).

At the heart of Cognitive Linguistics is the notion that language is not an autonomous system, but rather a reflection of our broader cognitive processes. This view challenges the traditional assumption that language can be studied in isolation, divorced from the wider context of human experience and understanding. Instead, Cognitive Linguistics posits that language is deeply intertwined with our perceptual, conceptual, and social faculties, and that the structures and patterns we observe in language can be best explained by reference to these underlying mental processes that shape our understanding and use of language (Chomsky, 2014).

One of the key tenets of Cognitive Linguistics is the idea that language is grounded in our embodied experience of the world.(Croft & Cruse, 2004) Rather than viewing language as a formal, rule-based system, Cognitive Linguists argue that our conceptual and linguistic structures are shaped by the way we physically interact with our environment, the way we perceive and categorize the world around us, and the social and cultural contexts in which we communicate.(Chomsky, 2014) This perspective has profound implications for how we approach the study of language, as it shifts the focus from abstract, decontextualized analyses to a more holistic understanding of language as a dynamic, situated phenomenon.

¹ Xolmanova Z. Tilshunoslikka kirish. www.ziyouz.com kutubxonasi

In terms of its internal structure, a language is a language with a certain amount of interdependence the sum of units and the use of these units is a complex system consisting of rules².

Language units, such as phonemes, morphemes, words, and sentences, are traditionally analyzed based on their structural properties. A cognitive approach, however, investigates how these units are represented and processed in the mind.

Phonemes, the smallest units of sound, are not just abstract entities but are linked to perceptual and motor processes. Research in cognitive phonology explores how phonemic distinctions are mentally represented and how they interact with other cognitive systems, such as memory and attention.

Morphemes, the smallest units of meaning, and words are analyzed in terms of their cognitive storage and retrieval. The mental lexicon, a cognitive construct, is believed to organize words based on semantic, phonological, and morphological properties, facilitating efficient language use and comprehension.

Sentences, as larger units of language, involve complex cognitive processes. Cognitive syntax examines how sentence structures are mentally represented and how syntactic processing interacts with other cognitive domains, such as working memory and semantic interpretation.

The relationship between language and thought is a central theme in cognitive linguistics. The Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, or linguistic relativity, posits that language shapes thought processes. While strong versions of this hypothesis are controversial, there is substantial evidence that language influences perception, categorization, and memory.

Cross-linguistic research provides insights into how different languages encode experiences and how this affects cognitive processes. For instance, languages with specific color terms can influence color perception, and languages with distinct spatial orientation systems can affect navigational abilities.

Advances in cognitive neuroscience have allowed researchers to investigate the neural correlates of language processing. Neuroimaging studies reveal how different brain regions are involved in various aspects of language, providing a biological basis for cognitive linguistic theories.

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